

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.6179 Max: 62.9072	1384 Natural + Anthropogenic

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 1724-1726
 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: reddish soil equivalent of 1199
 Covered by: SU: 1320, 1340
 Fills: SU: 1229
 Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (frequent, (medium), (rare)

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
☒ Pottery f ☒ Tiles f ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☒ Mortar r ☐ Coins ☒ Metal (specify) r ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	☒ Tufo (specify) f ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☒ Charcoal m ☐ Ash ☒ Animal bones f ☐ Human bones ☒ Animal teeth m ☐ Human teeth ☒ Shells r ☐ Other (specify)

SOIL/MATRIX
 clay 10% silt 85% sand 5%
 Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
☒ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	Black ☐ Brown Gray ☐ Light Brown Light Gray ☐ White Yellow ☐ Red Light Yellow Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: 1177 + 1199
 Is abutted by:
 Is covered by: 1320, 1340
 Is cut by:
 Is filled by:

Is bound to (only for masonry):
 Abuts: 1388
 Covers: 1401, 1230, 1410, 1394
 Cuts:
 Fills: 1229

OBSERVATIONS As excavation proceeded it was determined that the southern portion of SU 1384 should be designated a separate SU # and thus is SU 1388 soil over the rock (different compactness composition) for fewer finds, less hard, more clayey.

DESCRIPTION A414 Bronze fibula pin
 Position within sector: Southwest edge of Trench B, Northern limit of SU 1384
 Was 2010 excavation limit
 Shape: rectangular

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions): very slight downward slope to south
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): rubble running from south to north ending in central area - going off to the west
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): increase in thickness of central area towards south as underlying bedrock drops also thickness decreases on eastern side as
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify) tufo floor prep. rests to floor level.

Handwritten notes and a checkmark at the bottom of the sketch area.

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Reddish soil 1384 is equivalent to 1199 and fills cut 1229 of tufo floor in "courtyard" exposing drainage channel; ^{accumulation} layer/fill of various debris (pottery, tiles, bone, charcoal, etc). As excavation proceeded a large slab of tufo appeared on the western side of SU (covering drainage channel?) w/ tufo floor on top of southern side, additionally a bit further another large slab appeared and in line w/ this the soil changed to a less hard, more clayey soil w/ few finds and it was designated a separate SU, SU 1388 (which covers the step, threshold road).

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size: na

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by: CV, mm

on: July 12th 2011

Revised by: CHH

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